

ENGLISH BORROWINGS IN THE NEWSPAPER DISCOURSE OF FRANCE: THEIR FUNCTIONS AND ROLES

Adel Ilyasova^{1*}, Polina Ganzhelyuk², Tatiana Cherkasova³, Dilyara Vakhitova⁴

¹Ms., Senior lecturer, Kazan Federal University, Russian Federation, adeilyasova@gmail.com,

²Ms., Senior lecturer, Kazan Federal University, Russian Federation, polina5580@gmail.com

³Ms., Senior teacher, Kazan State University of Architecture and Engineering, kazimova_t@mail.ru

⁴Assoc. Prof., PhD in Philology, Kazan State University of Architecture and Engineering,

dilik15@yandex.ru

*Corresponding author

Abstract

This article is devoted to the study and analysis of the articles from a large French newspaper "Le Monde". The aim of this study is to identify English borrowings in the newspaper discourse. The process of borrowing is quite natural for any existing languages. However, it is significant to determine the function and role of the borrowed vocabulary in the language. In our article there are analyzed 96 articles, 24 articles per a sphere. There are four spheres: politics, economics, culture and sport. That is why according to the obtained results, it is identified that English borrowings are presented unevenly. The most amounts of borrowings is found in the articles dedicated to the sphere of culture and sport. The least amount of borrowings is found in articles on politics and economics. Among the found borrowings it is worth noting that most of them are different terms. It means that such borrowings enrich the language itself without replacing the original vocabulary of the language.

Keywords: borrowings, newspaper discourse, English, French

1. INTRODUCTION

For decades, the newspaper has been one of the most essential sources of information for residents of different countries. However, the newspaper itself has recently become a phenomenon which has been examined not only by journalists, but also by linguists. And this phenomenon has been considered as something unusual, independent, and which has its own language characteristics. The research is conducted in different directions, one of which is determined by the intention of modern linguistics to examine the communicative and cognitive issues that can permit to characterize the content of language form.

This article is dedicated to the analysis of peculiarities of use of English borrowings in French texts from the newspaper discourse. The relevance of the study is determined by the fact that, despite the attention to the sociolinguistic aspects of the problem of English borrowings in the French language, the peculiarities of use remain quite poorly examined. Furthermore, it is quite up-to-date aspect to examine them in the texts of newspapers, as it is proved by the huge impact of media in the modern society and understanding the fact that linguistic content of an article reflects the tendencies for the language development in general.

2. ANALYSIS

To conduct the analysis we have chosen articles from one of the largest French newspapers – ‘Le Monde’. In general we have analysed 96 articles, 24 articles from 4 different categories: Politics, Economics, Culture, Sports.

Fig. 1. Groups of found English borrowings

In the category of Politics there were found 6 articles with English borrowings:

«Plusieurs centaines de personnes ont continué d'occuper la place de la République, à Paris, tout **le week-end**»; «Réfugiés **welcome**»; «Tout en parlant à un homme qui le filme avec son **téléphone portable**» (organised according to the model from the English language - mobile phone); «Et que c'est pour tenter d'amadouer son **camp** que le chef d'Etat a modifié sa proposition initiale».

As it can be observed there are no specific political terms in these articles. And the borrowed words are simple English vocabulary.

Fig. 2. Politics

In the category of Economics there were found 7 articles with English borrowings:

«*Cette compétition rassemblera les meilleurs **jockeys** et **drivers** ainsi que les meilleurs trotteurs et galopeurs*»; «*Comme les réclameraient les **lobbys**, cette seconde option inquiète notamment les Verts européens*»; «*Lui veut croire que Kano peut continuer de rayonner dans tout le Sahel et rester le **hub** commercial si vital pour les pays voisins...*»; «*Afin d'enrayer la baisse de fréquentation, la SNCF et la SNCB font circuler à partir de ce dimanche des trains **lowcost** entre les deux capitales*».

Fig. 3. Economics

In the articles on economic topics, we have noted that the English borrowings are used to replace certain economic terms in French, and it is done, as we believe, to give more expressiveness to the text.

In the category of Culture there were found more English borrowings comparing to the articles of other topics. There were found 10 articles with the borrowed vocabulary. Moreover, there were some articles in which the English words appeared several times:

«*Dans le **hall** de la cité U de la rue de Bercypres de la gare de Lyon...*»; «*On ne saurait trop recommander la petite conque Cyrus North lui consacré sur le **Net***»; «*La face présente dans tous les **meetings** politiques et surtout les podiums de la joie, du très introuvable **free jazz***»; «***Star** ce de politique des années 1960 et 1970, compositeur de la B.O. du film culte de parla Bertolucci...*»; «*Du 29 au 31 mars, un poil de **cross-over**...*»; «*L'un des passeurs les plus célèbres du rapprochement de la country avec la variété **pop**...*»; «*Le festival Do Disturb vient irriguer et troubler les esprits, le temps d'un **week-end***»; La **start-up** française Iconem, experte de la numérisation 3D de sites archéologiques d'exception en danger, est sur la place».

As it can be understood, the English borrowings are quite comfortable in this category. We also paid attention to the fact that the most number of borrowings can be found in the articles with different genres of music.

Fig. 4. Culture

And, finally, among 24 articles from the Sports category, we have found 13 articles with the English borrowings. Sport news includes several use of the English vocabulary in the text of the same article:

«Les 11,5 millions de fichiers proviennent des archives du cabinet panaméen Mossack Fonseca, spécialiste de la domiciliation de sociétés **offshore**, entre 1977 et 2015»; «Dix ans après, ce **film** me permet justement de pouvoir exprimer...»; «Commerce n'était pas encore l'époque des **smartphones**, j'en ai pas tant d'images que ça»; «Chelsea est regardé partout, ses **fans** sont passionnés»; «Quelles conséquences auraient une mise à pied du **coach** marseillais»; «Le Barca semblait s'avancer inexorablement vers un nouveau triple Liga-Coupe-Ligue des **champions**...»; «L'Allemand a reçu un **choc** au genou»; «Le Racing 92 a réalisé un exploit en se qualifiant pour la première **demi-finale** européenne de son histoire» (here the French equivalent is based on the English model- semifinal).

Fig. 5. Sports

Fig. 6. Comparison in the amount of articles

3. CONCLUSIONS

This conducted analysis of journalistic texts allows us to conclude that in articles on various topics, English-language borrowings are unevenly distributed. For example, in publications on Politics and Economics, the number of borrowings turned out to be insignificant. Moreover, in most cases they are not political or economic terms, but words denoting publicly available realities. Articles from the category of culture include a significant number of English borrowings, which are often used as contextual synonyms of concepts already existing in the French language to achieve greater expressiveness, as well as designations of new concepts, trends, and ideas in the field of culture that arise in the United States and Great Britain. As for sports-related articles, they turned out to be peculiar leaders in the amount of the English vocabulary, which penetrated not only into French, but also into other languages of the world, which can also be explained by the lack of a suitable equivalent in the recipient language.

In general, it should be noted that our study clearly demonstrated the fact that today Anglicisms are quite widespread in use not only in newspaper headlines, which is usually done to attract the attention of readers, but also directly in the articles themselves.

In conclusion, we would like to note that English-language borrowings in French can be safely called an inexhaustible topic for research, since the dominance of English-speaking culture in the world and close contacts between the French- and English-speaking worlds indicate that the flow of borrowings is unlikely to stop in the near future.

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